

Science

SOME INCLUSION PROPERTIES FOR CERTAIN K-UNIFORMLY SUBCLASSES OF ANALYTIC FUNCTIONS ASSOCIATED WITH WRIGHT FUNCTION

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Abstract

A new operator $\mathbf{W}_{\lambda, \mu}^{\alpha} f(z) = z + \sum_{n \geq 2} \frac{4^{n-1} (\alpha)_{(n-1)} \Gamma(\lambda(n-1) + \mu)}{\Gamma(\mu)} a_n z^n$ is introduced for functions of the form $f(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n z^n$ which are analytic in the open unit disk $U = \{z \in \mathbb{C} : |z| < 1\}$. We introduce several inclusion properties of the new k -uniformly classes $US^*(\alpha; k; \gamma)$, $UC(\alpha; k; \gamma)$, $UK(\alpha; k; \gamma, \beta)$ and $UK^*(\alpha; k; \gamma, \beta)$ of analytic functions defined by using the Wright function with the operator $\mathbf{W}_{\lambda, \mu}^{\alpha}$ and the main object of this paper is to investigate various inclusion relationships for these classes. In addition, we proved that a special property is preserved by some integral operators.

Keywords: Analytic Functions; K-Uniformly Starlike Functions; K-Uniformly Convex Functions; K-Uniformly Close-To-Convex Functions; K-Uniformly Quasi-Convex Functions; Hadamard Product; Subordination.

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1. Introduction

Let $\mathbf{A}$ denote the class of functions of the form

$$f(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n z^n \quad (1.1)$$

Which are analytic in the open unit disk $U = \{z \in \mathbb{C} : |z| < 1\}$. If $\mathbf{f}$ and $\mathbf{g}$ are analytic in U , we say that f is subordinate to g , written $f \prec g$ or $f(z) \prec g(z)$, if there exists a Schwarz

function ω , analytic in $\mathbf{U}$ with $\omega(0)=0$ and $|\omega(z)| < 1$ ($z \in \mathbf{U}$) , such that $f(z) = g(\omega(z))$ ($z \in \mathbf{U}$) . In particular, if the function g is univalent in $\mathbf{U}$, the above subordination is equivalent to $f(0) = g(0)$ and $f(\mathbf{U}) \subset g(\mathbf{U})$ (see [9] and [10]).

For functions $f(z) \in \mathbf{A}$, given by (1.1) , and $g(z) \in \mathbf{A}$ defined by

$$g(z) = z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} b_k z^k ,$$

then the Hadamard product (or convolution) of $f(z)$ and $g(z)$ is given by

$$(f * g)(z) = z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} a_k b_k z^k = (g * f)(z) \quad (z \in U).$$

For $0 \leq \gamma, \beta < 1$, we denote by $S^*(\gamma)$, $C(\gamma)$, $K(\gamma, \beta)$ and $K^*(\gamma, \beta)$ the subclasses of $\mathbf{A}$ consisting of all analytic functions which are, respectively, starlike of order γ , convex of order γ , close-to-convex of order γ , and type β and quasi-convex of order γ , and type β in $\mathbf{U}$.

Now, we introduce the subclasses $US^*(k; \gamma)$, $UC(k; \gamma)$, $UK(k; \gamma, \beta)$ and $UK^*(k; \gamma, \beta)$ of the class $\mathbf{A}$ for $0 \leq \gamma, \beta < 1$, and $k \geq 0$, which are defined by

$$US^*(k; \gamma) = \left\{ f \in \mathbf{A} : \Re \left(\frac{zf'(z)}{f(z)} - \gamma \right) > k \left| \frac{zf'(z)}{f(z)} - 1 \right| \right\}, \tag{1.2}$$

$$UC(k; \gamma) = \left\{ f \in \mathbf{A} : \Re \left(1 + \frac{zf''(z)}{f'(z)} - \gamma \right) > k \left| \frac{zf''(z)}{f'(z)} \right| + \gamma \right\}, \tag{1.3}$$

$$UK(k; \gamma, \beta) = \left\{ f \in \mathbf{A} : \exists g \in US^*(k; \beta) \text{ s.t. } \Re \left(\frac{zf'(z)}{g(z)} - \gamma \right) > k \left| \frac{zf'(z)}{g(z)} - 1 \right| \right\}, \tag{1.4}$$

$$UK^*(k; \gamma, \beta) = \left\{ f \in \mathbf{A} : \exists g \in UC(k; \gamma) \text{ s.t. } \Re \left(\frac{(zf'(z))'}{g'(z)} - \gamma \right) > k \left| \frac{(zf'(z))'}{g'(z)} - 1 \right| \right\}. \tag{1.5}$$

We note that

$$\left. \begin{aligned} US^*(0; \gamma) &= S^*(k; \gamma), UC(0; \gamma) = C(\gamma), \\ UK(0; \gamma, \beta) &= K(\gamma, \beta), UK^*(0; \gamma, \beta) = K^*(\gamma, \beta) \quad (0 \leq \gamma, \beta < 1). \end{aligned} \right\}$$

Corresponding to a conic domain $\Omega_{k,\gamma}$ defined by

$$\Omega_{k,\gamma} = \left\{ u + iv : u > k\sqrt{(u-1)^2 + v^2} + \gamma \right\} \tag{1.6}$$

we define the function $q_{k,\gamma}(z)$ which maps $\mathbf{U}$ onto the conic domain $\Omega_{k,\gamma}$ such that $1 \in \Omega_{k,\gamma}$ as the following:

$$q_{k,\gamma}(z) = \begin{cases} \frac{1+(1-2\gamma)z}{1-z} & (k=0), \\ \frac{1-\gamma}{1-k^2} \cos\left\{\frac{2}{\pi}(\cos^{-1}k)\right\} i \log \frac{1+\sqrt{z}}{1-\sqrt{z}} - \frac{k^2-\gamma}{1-k^2} & (0 < k < 1), \\ 1 + \frac{2(1-\gamma)}{\pi^2} \left(\log \frac{1+\sqrt{z}}{1-\sqrt{z}}\right)^2 & (k=1), \\ \frac{1-\gamma}{k^2-1} \sin\left\{\frac{\pi}{2\zeta(k)} \int_0^{\frac{u(z)}{\sqrt{k}}} \frac{dt}{\sqrt{1-t^2}\sqrt{1-k^2t^2}}\right\} + \frac{k^2-\gamma}{k^2-1} & (k > 1). \end{cases} \tag{1.7}$$

Where $u(z) = \frac{z-\sqrt{k}}{1-\sqrt{kz}}$ and $\zeta(k)$ is such that $k = \cosh \frac{\pi\zeta'(z)}{4\zeta(z)}$. By virtue of the properties of the conic domain $\Omega_{k,\gamma}$, we have

$$\Re\{q_{k,\gamma}(z)\} > \frac{k+\gamma}{k+1}. \tag{1.8}$$

Making use of the principal of subordination and the definition of $q_{k,\gamma}(z)$, we may rewrite the subclasses $US^*(k;\gamma)$, $UC(k;\gamma)$, $UK(k;\gamma,\beta)$ and $UK^*(k;\gamma,\beta)$ as the following:

$$US^*(k;\gamma) = \left\{ f \in \mathbf{A} : \frac{zf'(z)}{f(z)} \prec q_{k,\gamma}(z) \right\}, \tag{1.9}$$

$$UC(k;\gamma) = \left\{ f \in \mathbf{A} : 1 + \frac{zf''(z)}{f'(z)} \prec q_{k,\gamma}(z) \right\}, \tag{1.10}$$

$$UK(k;\gamma,\beta) = \left\{ f \in \mathbf{A} : \exists g \in US^*(k;\beta) \text{ s.t. } \frac{zf'(z)}{g(z)} \prec q_{k,\gamma}(z) \right\}, \tag{1.11}$$

$$UK^*(k;\gamma,\beta) = \left\{ f \in \mathbf{A} : \exists g \in UC(k;\gamma) \text{ s.t. } \frac{(zf'(z))'}{g'(z)} \prec q_{k,\gamma}(z) \right\}. \tag{1.12}$$

We consider the following normalized form

$$\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}(z) = \Gamma(\mu)z\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}\left(\frac{z}{4}\right) = \sum_{n \geq 0} \frac{\Gamma(\mu)z^{n+1}}{4^n n! \Gamma(\lambda n + \mu)},$$

where $\lambda \geq -1, \mu \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{Z}_0^-, z \in U$. Note that the normalized wright function $\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}$ was studied recently in [13].

Now, we define an operator $\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}$ as follows:

$$\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}f(z) = \mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}(z) * f(z) = z + \sum_{n \geq 2} \frac{\Gamma(\mu)}{4^{n-1}(n-1)! \Gamma(\lambda(n-1) + \mu)} a_n z^n, \tag{1.13}$$

where $\lambda \geq -1, \mu \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{Z}_0^-, z \in U$. Note that, if $f(z) = \frac{z}{(1-z)}$ then the operator $\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}f(z)$ reduces to the functions

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{w}_{\nu,b,c}(z) &= \mathbf{w}_{1,\nu+\frac{b+1}{2}}(-cz) * \frac{z}{1-z} = (-c)2^\nu \Gamma(\nu + (b+1)/2) z^{1-\nu/2} \mathbf{w}_{\nu,b,c}(\sqrt{z}), \\ (1.1)4 \quad g_\nu(z) &= \mathbf{w}_{1,\nu+1}(-z) * \frac{z}{1-z} = (-1)2^\nu \Gamma(\nu+1)/2 z^{1-\nu/2} \mathbf{J}_\nu(\sqrt{z}) \end{aligned}$$

And

$$\mathbf{K}_\nu(z) = \mathbf{w}_{1,\nu+1}\left(\frac{z}{1-z}\right) = \mathbf{w}_{1,\nu+1}(z) * \frac{z}{1-z} = 2^\nu \Gamma(\nu+1) z^{1-\nu/2} \mathbf{I}_\nu(\sqrt{z}). \tag{1.15}$$

Note that the function $\mathbf{v}_{\nu,b,c}(z)$ was studied recently in [1, 2, 11] and $\mathbf{g}_\nu(z)$ was investigated in [3, 12, 14].

Corresponding to the function $\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}(z)$ defined by (1.13), we introduce a function $\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha(z)$ given by

$$\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}(z) * \mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha(z) = \frac{z}{(1-z)^\alpha} \quad (\alpha > 0). \tag{1.16}$$

We now define an operator $\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha f(z): \mathbf{A} \rightarrow \mathbf{A}$ by

$$\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha f(z) = \mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha(z) * f(z) \tag{1.17}$$

$$(\lambda \geq -1, \mu \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{Z}_0^-, \alpha > 0; z \in U).$$

If $f(z)$ is given by (1.1) , then from (1.17) , we deduce that

$$\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha f(z) = z + \sum_{n \geq 2} \frac{4^{n-1}(\alpha)_{(n-1)}\Gamma(\lambda(n-1) + \mu)}{\Gamma(\mu)} a_n z^n \tag{1.18}$$

$(\lambda \geq -1, \mu \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{Z}_0^-, \alpha > 0; z \in U).$

It is easily to deduce from (1.18) that.

$$z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha f(z))' = \alpha(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^{\alpha+1} f(z)) - (\alpha - 1)(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha f(z)) \tag{1.19}$$

Next, by using the operator $\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha$, we introduce the following classes of analytic functions for $\lambda \geq -1, \mu \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{Z}_0^-, \alpha > 0, k \geq 0$ and $0 \leq \gamma, \beta < 1$:

$$US^*(\alpha; k; \gamma) = \{f \in \mathbf{A} : \mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha f(z) \in US^*(k; \gamma)\}, \tag{1.20}$$

$$UC(\alpha; k; \gamma) = \{f \in \mathbf{A} : \mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha f(z) \in UC(k; \gamma)\}, \tag{1.21}$$

$$UK(\alpha; k; \gamma, \beta) = \{f \in \mathbf{A} : \mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha f(z) \in UK(k; \gamma, \beta)\}, \tag{1.22}$$

$$UK^*(\alpha; k; \gamma, \beta) = \{f \in \mathbf{A} : \mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha f(z) \in UK^*(k; \gamma, \beta)\}, \tag{1.23}$$

We also note that

$$f(z) \in US^*(\alpha; k; \gamma) \Leftrightarrow zf'(z) \in UC(\alpha; k; \gamma),$$

and

$$f(z) \in UK(\alpha; k; \gamma, \beta) \Leftrightarrow zf'(z) \in UK^*(\alpha; k; \gamma, \beta). \tag{1.24}$$

In this paper, we investigate several inclusion properties of the classes $US^*(\alpha; k; \gamma)$, $UC(\alpha; k; \gamma)$, $UK(\alpha; k; \gamma, \beta)$ and $UK^*(\alpha; k; \gamma, \beta)$ associated with the operator $\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha$. Some applications involving integral operators are also considered.

2. Inclusion Properties Involving the Operator $\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha$

In order to prove the main results, we shall need the following lemmas.

Lemma 1 [5]. *Let $h(z)$ be convex univalent in $\mathbf{U}$ with $h(0)=1$ and $\Re\{\eta h(z) + \gamma\} > 0$ ($\eta, \gamma \in \mathbb{C}$) . If $p(z)$ is analytic in $\mathbf{U}$ with $p(0)=1$, then*

$$p(z) + \frac{zp'(z)}{\eta p(z) + \gamma} \prec h(z) \tag{2.1}$$

Implies

$$p(z) \prec h(z). \tag{2.2}$$

Lemma 2 [8]. Let $h(z)$ be convex univalent in $\mathbf{U}$ and let w be analytic in $\mathbf{U}$ with $\Re\{w(z)\} \geq 0$. If $p(z)$ is analytic in $\mathbf{U}$ and $p(0) = h(0)$, then

$$p(z) + w(z)zp'(z) \prec h(z) \tag{2.3}$$

Implies

$$p(z) \prec h(z). \tag{2.4}$$

Theorem 1. $US^*(\alpha + 1; k; \gamma) \subset US^*(\alpha; k; \gamma)$.

Proof. Let $f \in US^*(\alpha + 1; k; \gamma)$ and set

$$p(z) = \frac{z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha f(z))'}{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha f(z)} \quad (z \in \mathbf{U}), \tag{2.5}$$

where $p(z)$ is analytic in $\mathbf{U}$ with $p(0) = 1$. From (1.19) and (2.5), we have

$$\frac{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^{\alpha+1} f(z)}{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha f(z)} = \frac{1}{\alpha} \{p(z) + (\alpha - 1)\}. \tag{2.6}$$

Differentiating (2.6) with respect to z and multiplying the result equation by z , we obtain

$$\frac{z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^{\alpha+1} f(z))'}{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^{\alpha+1} f(z)} = p(z) + \frac{zp'(z)}{p(z) + (\alpha - 1)}. \tag{2.7}$$

From this and the argument given in Section 1, we may write

$$p(z) + \frac{zp'(z)}{p(z) + (\alpha - 1)} \prec q_{k, \gamma}(z) \quad (z \in \mathbf{U}). \tag{2.8}$$

Since $(\alpha - 1) > 0$ and $\Re\{q_{k, \gamma}(z)\} > \frac{k + \gamma}{k + 1}$, we see that

$$\Re\{q_{k,\gamma}(z) + (\alpha - 1)\} > 0 \quad (z \in \mathbf{U}). \tag{2.9}$$

Applying Lemma 1 to (2.8), it follows that $p(z) \prec q_{k,\gamma}(z)$, that is, $f \in US^*(\alpha; k; \gamma)$.

Theorem 2. $UC(\alpha + 1; k; \gamma) \subset UC(\alpha; k; \gamma)$.

Proof. Applying (1.24) and Theorem 1, we observe that

$$\begin{aligned} f(z) \in UC(\alpha + 1; k; \gamma) &\Leftrightarrow zf'(z) \in US^*(\alpha + 1; k; \gamma) \\ &\Rightarrow zf'(z) \in US^*(\alpha; k; \gamma) \\ &\Leftrightarrow f(z) \in UC(\alpha; k; \gamma), \end{aligned}$$

which evidently proves Theorem 2.

Theorem 3. $UK(\alpha + 1; k; \gamma, \beta) \subset UK(\alpha; k; \gamma, \beta)$.

Proof. Let $f \in UK(\alpha + 1; k; \gamma, \beta)$. Then, from the definition of $UK(\alpha + 1; k; \gamma, \beta)$, there exists a function $r(z) \in US^*(k; \gamma)$ such that

$$\frac{z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^{\alpha+1} f(z))'}{r(z)} \prec q_{k,\gamma}(z). \tag{2.10}$$

Choose the function $g(z)$ such that $\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^{\alpha+1} g(z) = r(z)$. Then, $g \in US^*(\alpha + 1; k; \gamma)$ and

$$\frac{z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^{\alpha+1} f(z))'}{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^{\alpha+1} g(z)} \prec q_{k,\gamma}(z). \tag{2.11}$$

Now let

$$p(z) = \frac{z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^{\alpha} f(z))'}{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^{\alpha} g(z)}, \tag{2.12}$$

where $p(z)$ is analytic in $\mathbf{U}$ with $p(0) = 1$. Since $g \in US^*(\alpha + 1; k; \gamma)$, by Theorem 1, we know that $g \in US^*(\alpha; k; \gamma)$. Let

$$t(z) = \frac{z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^{\alpha} g(z))'}{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^{\alpha} g(z)} \quad (z \in \mathbf{U}), \tag{2.13}$$

where $t(z)$ is analytic in $\mathbf{U}$ with $\Re\{t(z)\} > \frac{k+\gamma}{k+1}$. Also, from (2.13), we note that

$$z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^{\alpha} f(z))' = \mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^{\alpha} zf'(z) = (\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^{\alpha} g(z)) p(z). \tag{2.14}$$

Differentiating both sides of (2.14) with respect to z and multiplying the result equation by z , we obtain

$$\frac{z(\mathbf{W}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha z f'(z))'}{\mathbf{W}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha g(z)} = \frac{z(\mathbf{W}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha g(z))'}{\mathbf{W}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha g(z)} p(z) + zp'(z) = t(z)p(z) + zp'(z). \tag{2.15}$$

Now using the identity (1.19) and (2.15), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{z(\mathbf{W}_{\lambda,\mu}^{\alpha+1} f(z))'}{\mathbf{W}_{\lambda,\mu}^{\alpha+1} g(z)} &= \frac{\mathbf{W}_{\lambda,\mu}^{\alpha+1} z f'(z)}{\mathbf{W}_{\lambda,\mu}^{\alpha+1} g(z)} = \frac{z(\mathbf{W}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha z f'(z))' + (\alpha - 1)\mathbf{W}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha z f'(z)}{z(\mathbf{W}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha g(z))' + (\alpha - 1)\mathbf{W}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha g(z)} \\ &= \frac{\frac{z(\mathbf{W}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha z f'(z))'}{\mathbf{W}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha g(z)} + (\alpha - 1)\frac{z(\mathbf{W}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha f(z))'}{\mathbf{W}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha g(z)}}{\frac{z(\mathbf{W}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha g(z))'}{\mathbf{W}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha g(z)} + (\alpha - 1)} \\ &= \frac{t(z)p(z) + zp'(z) + (\alpha - 1)p(z)}{t(z) + (\alpha - 1)} \\ (2.16) \qquad \qquad \qquad &= p(z) + \frac{zp'(z)}{t(z) + (\alpha - 1)}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $(\alpha - 1) > 0$ and $\Re\{t(z)\} > \frac{k + \gamma}{k + 1}$, we see that

$$\Re\{t(z) + (\alpha - 1)\} > 0 \quad (z \in \mathbf{U}). \tag{2.17}$$

Hence, applying Lemma 2, we can show that $p(z) \prec_{k,\gamma} q_{k,\gamma}(z)$ so that $f \in UK(\alpha; k; \gamma, \beta)$. This completes the proof of Theorem 3.

Theorem 4. $UK^*(\alpha + 1; k; \gamma, \beta) \subset UK^*(\alpha; k; \gamma, \beta)$.

Proof. Just as we derived Theorem 2 as consequence of Theorem 1 by using the equivalence (1.24), we can also prove Theorem 4 by using Theorem 3 and the equivalence (1.25).

3. Inclusion Properties Involving the Integral Operator F_c

In this section, we consider the generalized Libera integral operator F_c (see [4, 6, 7]) defined by

$$F_c(f)(z) = \frac{c+1}{z^c} \int_0^z t^{c-1} f(t) dt \quad (f \in \mathbf{A}; c > -1). \tag{3.1}$$

Theorem 5. Let $c > -\frac{k+\gamma}{k+1}$. If $f \in US^*(\alpha; k; \gamma)$, then $F_c(f) \in US^*(\alpha; k; \gamma)$.

Proof. Let $f \in US^*(\alpha; k; \gamma)$ and set

$$p(z) = \frac{z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha F_c(f)(z))'}{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha F_c(f)(z)} \quad (z \in \mathbf{U}), \tag{3.2}$$

where $p(z)$ is analytic in $\mathbf{U}$ with $p(0) = 1$. From (3.2), we have

$$z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha F_c(f)(z))' = (c+1)\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha f(z) - c\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha F_c(f)(z). \tag{3.3}$$

Then, by using (3.2) and (3.3), we obtain

$$(c+1) \frac{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha f(z)}{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha F_c(f)(z)} = p(z) + c. \tag{3.4}$$

Taking the logarithmic differentiation on both sides of (3.4) and multiplying by z , we have

$$p(z) + \frac{zp'(z)}{p(z) + c} = \frac{z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha f(z))'}{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha f(z)} \prec q_{k, \gamma}(z). \tag{3.5}$$

Hence, by virtue of Lemma 1, we conclude that $p(z) \prec q_{k, \gamma}(z)$ in $\mathbf{U}$, which implies that $F_c(f) \in US^*(\alpha; k; \gamma)$.

Theorem 6. Let $c > -\frac{k+\gamma}{k+1}$. If $f \in UC(\alpha; k; \gamma)$, then $F_c(f) \in UC(\alpha; k; \gamma)$.

Proof. By applying Theorem 5, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} f(z) \in UC(\alpha; k; \gamma) &\Leftrightarrow zf'(z) \in US^*(\alpha; k; \gamma) \\ &\Rightarrow F_c(zf')(z) \in US^*(\alpha; k; \gamma) \quad (\text{by Theorem 5}) \\ &\Leftrightarrow z(F_c(f)(z))' \in US^*(\alpha; k; \gamma) \end{aligned}$$

$$(3.6) \qquad \qquad \qquad \Leftrightarrow F_c(f)(z) \in UC(\alpha; k; \gamma),$$

which proves Theorem 6.

Theorem 7. Let $c > -\frac{k+\gamma}{k+1}$. If $f \in UK(\alpha; k; \gamma, \beta)$, then $F_c(f) \in UK(\alpha; k; \gamma, \beta)$.

Proof. Let $f \in UK(\alpha; k; \gamma, \beta)$. Then, in view of the definition of the class $UK(\alpha; k; \gamma, \beta)$, there exists a function $g \in US^*(\alpha; k; \gamma)$ such that

$$\frac{z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha f(z))'}{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha g(z)} \prec q_{k, \gamma}(z). \tag{3.7}$$

Thus, we set

$$p(z) = \frac{z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha F_c(f)(z))'}{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha F_c(g)(z)} \quad (z \in \mathbf{U}), \tag{3.8}$$

where $p(z)$ is analytic in $\mathbf{U}$ with $p(0) = 1$. Since $g \in US^*(\alpha; k; \gamma)$, we see from Theorem 5. that $F_c(g) \in US^*(\alpha; k; \gamma)$. Using (3.3) and let

$$t(z) = \frac{z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha F_c(g)(z))'}{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha F_c(g)(z)}, \tag{3.9}$$

where $t(z)$ is analytic in $\mathbf{U}$ with $\Re\{t(z)\} > \frac{k+\gamma}{k+1}$. Using (3.8), we have

$$\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha zF_c'(f)(z) = (\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha F_c(g)(z)) p(z). \tag{3.10}$$

Differentiating both sides of (3.10) with respect to z and multiplying by z , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha zF_c'(f)(z))'}{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha F_c(g)(z)} &= \frac{z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha F_c(f)(z))'}{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda, \mu}^\alpha F_c(g)(z)} p(z) + zp'(z) \\ &= t(z)p(z) + zp'(z). \end{aligned} \tag{3.11}$$

Now using the identity (3.3) and (3.11), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha f(z))'}{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha g(z)} &= \frac{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha z f'(z)}{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha g(z)} = \frac{z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha z F_c'(f)(z))' + c \mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha z F_c'(f)(z)}{z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha F_c(g)(z))' + c \mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha F_c(g)(z)} \\
 &= \frac{\frac{z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha z F_c'(f)(z))'}{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha F_c(g)(z)} + c \frac{z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha F_c(f)(z))'}{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha F_c(g)(z)}}{\frac{z(\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha F_c(g)(z))'}{\mathbf{w}_{\lambda,\mu}^\alpha F_c(g)(z)} + c} \\
 &= \frac{t(z)p(z) + zp'(z) + cp(z)}{t(z) + c} \\
 (3.12) \qquad \qquad \qquad &= p(z) + \frac{zp'(z)}{t(z) + c}
 \end{aligned}$$

Since $c > -\frac{k+\gamma}{k+1}$ and $\Re\{t(z)\} > \frac{k+\gamma}{k+1}$, we see that

$$\Re\{t(z) + c\} > 0 \quad (z \in \mathbf{U}). \tag{3.13}$$

Applying Lemma 2 to (3.12), it follows that $p(z) \prec_{q_{k,\gamma}}(z)$, that is $F_c(f) \in UK(\alpha; k; \gamma, \beta)$.

Theorem 8. Let $c > -\frac{k+\gamma}{k+1}$. If $f \in UK^*(\alpha; k; \gamma, \beta)$, then $F_c(f) \in UK^*(\alpha; k; \gamma, \beta)$.

Proof. Just as we derived Theorem 6 as consequence of Theorem 5 and (1.24), we easily deduce the integral-preserving property asserted by Theorem 8 by using Theorem 7 and (1.25).

Reference

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